

COORDINATED SPECIFICATION AND QUANTITY TAKE-OFF THROUGH DIGITAL MODELLING

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Supervisor

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Abstract

Even though BIM-based specification and quantity take-off are more efficient than traditional methods (Olsen and Taylor, 2017; Khosakitchalart, Yabuki and Fukuda, 2019), they still have a vast space for further developments which would enable them to reach higher degrees of digitalization. Both processes still lack integration and are not entirely automatized, requiring the information to flow within different BIM platforms, demanding some time-consuming and error-prone human interventions. Also, BIM-based solutions for specification and quantity take-off can be expensive and not compliant with some needs for customization to better adapt to companies internal workflows. This problematization led this work to the following question: How to re-engineer BIM-based specification and quantity take-off processes in order to make them more automatized, accurate, integrated, faster and cheaper?

This dissertation addressed the problem by developing an add-in through the API of a specific BIM authoring tool, found on a proposed framework that comprises standards, information modelling and database management issues. The developed tool is a BIM-based digital solution which automatically generates a coordinated report for specification and quantity take-off, setting up also a preliminary cost estimation. It extracts, matches and combines information from a BIM model and a database, based on a classification system.

Alongside the literature review, the work methodology leaned on a study object, the architectural office Marta Campos Atelier de Arquitectura based in Porto, Portugal. It diagnosed their current workflow, mapping the process AS-IS for specification and quantity take-off. Next, it performed its assessment and finally proposed the framework which comprises the re-engineered process TO-BE, embedded in the developed digital solution. In the end, the add-in was executed in real case scenarios, on two ongoing projects at the study object firm, and

successfully produced the expected outcome, the coordinated specification and quantity take-off report (in Portugal commonly called “Mapa de Trabalhos e Quantidades”).

The re-engineered BIM-based specification and quantity take-off embedded by the proposed framework alongside the developed digital tool enabled a more integrated, automatized and faster generation of the coordinated specification, quantity take-off and preliminary cost estimation report. The whole re-engineered process (TO-BE) took 1/5 of the time than the AS-IS (performed in the current workflow) and was able to limit the manual interventions for the modelling activities. The TO-BE process added value to the firm business model, accomplishing a higher degree of digitalization.

Dissertation:

<https://bimaplus.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/2020-LucasVieira-Dissertation.pdf>

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/zHsB3CtMzUY>

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